

UNLOCKING SECTION 3(1) OF SRI LANKA'S BAIL ACT

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1. OVERVIEW

'Twas in mid-1998 that much debate arose, within Sri Lanka's legal fraternity, regarding the emergent proclivity of courts to release 'special law' offenders (suspected of possessing prohibited drugs, firearms, explosives, *etc.*) under the 'general law' criteria for granting bail as restated by the Bail Act No.30 of 1997 (hereinafter 'Bail Act [1997]'), instead of enforcing the more stringent bail conditions specified by previous legislatures from time to time.

This divergence was rooted in the premise that section 3(1), as complemented by section 27,¹ vested in the said Bail Act [1997] 'supremacy' over any other written law (both extant and future) to the contrary. To this end, much reliance was placed on the speech made by the then 'Minister of Justice and Constitutional Affairs' when introducing the Bail Bill to Parliament, wherein, among other things, the government made manifest its intention to include all offenses within the scope of the Bail Act except those against national security or public order that already had special bail provisions expressed in respect thereof.

The superior courts of Sri Lanka had not, at such time, definitively decided on whether Hansard could or could not be referred to (as an 'extrinsic aid') in determining the meaning of any provision enacted by the legislature.

Hence, prior to ascertaining, from the words articulated by the 'Minister' in his said 'speech,' the particular purpose for which section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997] was enacted, it becomes essential to establish whether Hansard itself is admissible under the law of Sri Lanka for eliciting the intent underlying a statutory provision.

2. LEGAL COGNIZABILITY OF HANSARD DISCLOSURES AS AN AID TO INTERPRETATION

The esteemed law lords of Sri Lanka have more often than not deferred to the *dicta* of their counterparts in the United Kingdom in this regard. Hence, the conventional Sri Lankan position on this issue received enunciation by the Court of Appeal in *J. B. Textiles Industries Limited v. Minister of Finance and Planning* [1981] as follows:

... Speeches made in Parliament, in the course of the debate when a bill is presented to Parliament, cannot be referred to in court as an aid in the construction of the provisions of a statute. ... Any reference or inquiry by a court into anything that is alleged to have been said or done by a Member of Parliament during the various stages of the progress of a bill through Parliament may involve an adjudication by court, which the court is not competent to undertake. If, as is clear, a court cannot take into consideration anything said or done in Parliament to aid it in the construction of a provision of a statute passed by Parliament itself, still less legitimate would it be for the court to take into consideration anything so said and done for any other purpose (e.g., 'for the purpose of supporting a cause of action even though the cause of action itself arose out of something done outside Parliament').² (Per Ranasinghe J., 262, parenthesis added.)

Furthermore, in the subsequent Supreme Court determination of the very same *J. B. Textiles Ltd. v. Minister of Finance* [1981], Samarakoon C.J. took exception only to Ranasinghe J.'s final caution (above), namely, that anything said or done in Parliament could not be cited in court, even for purposes other than interpretation.

Categorically referring to Ranasinghe J.'s reliance on *Davis v. Johnson* [1979], 337, wherein Viscount Dilhorne had declared *inter alia* that 'It is a well and long established rule that counsel cannot refer to Hansard as an aid to the construction of a statute,' Samarakoon C.J. proceeded to deem this 'rule' as 'well established and well known,' averring further that he did not view the same as having 'any relevance' to the question that arose for decision by the court (*J. B. Textiles Ltd. v. Minister of Finance* [1981], 161).

Thus, neither of the two superior courts to which *J. B. Textiles Industries Limited v. Minister of Finance and Planning* [1981] was petitioned saw fit to depart from the conventional rule that Hansard was inadmissible to aid in statutory interpretation.

As far as Sri Lanka is concerned, the first pronouncement regarding the possibility of having recourse to ministerial speeches made in parliament on proposed legislation – strictly for purposes of construing the provisions so introduced – appears to have been that made by Vythialingam J. as early as in 1974:

I am of the view that we ought not to do so (*i.e.*, ‘look at the Hansard ... and ascertain the intention of Parliament’) **unless there is such great ambiguity in the words that looking at Hansard alone would be decisive.** (*Sirisena and others v. Kobbekaduwa, Minister of Agriculture and Lands* [1978], 71, parenthesis and emphasis added.)

Approximately thirteen years later, in 1987, Sharvananda C.J. – although having *carte blanche* to denounce the State’s quoting from Hansard in furtherance of evincing legislative intent – chose instead to opine as follows:

He (State Counsel) referred to the espousal of the object that the minister had in mind when introducing the bill for effecting the Amendment No.13 of 1982. *Vide* Hansard dated 25.2.1982, vol.9 part 19, at pages 1558-1559, the minister said, ‘*It is necessary in the situation that we are faced with, where forest resources are fast depleting, to see that strong and firm action is taken, although in the process some innocent people might suffer.*’ **I see the force of Counsel’s argument.** However, a construction which offends justice and is repugnant to the Rule of Law that permeates our Constitution should yield to an alternate construction which is in harmony with justice and human rights. (*Manawadu v. Attorney General* [1987], 40, parenthesis and emphasis added.) ... I am unable to accept the submission of State Counsel that the legislature, by section 7 of Act No.13 of 1982, intended to deprive an owner of his vehicle that had been used by the offender in committing a forest offense without the owner’s knowledge and without his participation. Having regard to the inequitable consequences that flow from treating the words ‘shall by reason of such conviction be forfeited to the state’ as mandatory, I am inclined to hold ... that ‘forfeited’ meant ‘liable to be forfeited,’ and thus avoid the injustice that would flow from the construction that

forfeiture of the vehicle is automatic on the conviction of the accused. (*Manawadu v. Attorney General* [1987], 43.)

The State's contention was dismissed not for any want of admissibility regarding the pertinent Hansard's words, but rather for what they did confirm: the impugned provision was *ab initio* arbitrary (which the rule of law could not permit). What Sharvananda C.J. chose to refute was the propriety of the legislature's intent *per se*, not the propriety of having recourse to Hansard for evincing it. Thus, recourse to Hansard for evincing legislative intent appears to have been tacitly approved of.

Seventeen years later, in 2004, Sriskandarajah J. declared the U.K. House of Lords' determination in *Pepper (Inspector of Taxes) v. Hart* [1993] (hereinafter '*Pepper v. Hart* [1993]') as providing the necessary impetus to legitimize, within Sri Lanka, recourse to speeches made in Parliament concerning the passing of a Bill in order to 'clarify the ambiguity' occasioned by any provision of the final Act (*Gunasekera and others v. Ravi Karunanayake* [2005], 25). In proceeding to declare thus, Sriskandarajah J. chose to cite only the following finding of Lord Browne-Wilkinson J. (made on the question '*Should the rule prohibiting references to parliamentary material be relaxed?*')

I therefore reach the conclusion (subject to any question of parliamentary privilege) **to permit reference to parliamentary materials where** (a) **legislation is ambiguous or obscure** or leads to an absurdity; (b) the material relied upon consists of **one or more statements by a minister** or other **promoter of the bill** together, if necessary, with such other parliamentary material as is necessary to understand such statements and their effect; (c) the statements relied upon are **clear**. (*Pepper v. Hart* [1993], 640, emphasis and brackets added.)

It would not be unreasonable to assume that much more in terms of rationale was in fact gleaned by Sriskandarajah J. from the following:

... Reference to parliamentary material should be permitted as an aid to the construction of legislation which is **ambiguous or obscure** (or the literal meaning of which leads to an absurdity). Even in such cases, references in court to parliamentary material should only be permitted where such material clearly discloses (the mischief aimed at or) the legislative intention lying behind the **ambiguous or obscure** words. In the case of statements made in Parliament, as at present advised, I cannot foresee that any statement other than the statement of the minister or other **promoter of the bill** is likely to meet these criteria. (*Pepper v. Hart* [1993], per Lord Browne-Wilkinson J., 634, brackets and emphasis added.)

... My main reason for reaching this conclusion is based on principle. Statute law consists of the words that Parliament has enacted. It is for the courts to construe those words, and it is the court's duty in so doing to give effect to the intention of Parliament in using those words. It is an inescapable fact that despite all the care taken in passing legislation, some statutory provisions, when applied to the circumstances under consideration in any specific case, are found to be **ambiguous**. ... **Parliament never intends to enact an ambiguity**. ... In many, I suspect most, cases references to parliamentary materials will not throw any light on the matter. But in a few cases, it **may emerge that the very question was considered by Parliament in passing the legislation**. Why in such a case should the courts blind themselves to a clear indication of what Parliament intended in using those words? The court cannot attach a meaning to words which they cannot bear, but if the words are capable of bearing more than one meaning, why should not Parliament's true intention be enforced rather than thwarted? (*Pepper v. Hart* [1993], per Lord Browne-Wilkinson J., 634-635, emphasis added.)

The courts should not deny themselves the light which parliamentary materials may shed on the meaning of the words Parliament has used and thereby risk subjecting the individual to a law which Parliament never intended to enact. (*Pepper v. Hart* [1993], per Lord Browne-Wilkinson J., 638.)

The object of the court in interpreting legislation is to give effect, so far as the language permits, to the intention of the legislature. If the language proves to be **ambiguous**, I can see no sound reason not to consult Hansard to see if there is a clear statement of the meaning that the words were intended to carry. The days have long passed when the courts adopted a strict constructionist view of interpretation, which required them to adopt the literal meaning of the language. The courts now adopt a purposive approach, which seeks to give effect to the true purpose of legislation, and are prepared to look at much extraneous material that bears upon the background against which the legislation was enacted. Why then cut ourselves off from the one source in

which may be found an authoritative statement of the intention with which the legislation is placed before Parliament? (*Pepper v. Hart* [1993], per Lord Griffiths J., 617, emphasis added.)

Thus, *Pepper v. Hart's* emphasis on resolving a statutory provision's otherwise unresolvable ambiguity by referring to clear proponent disclosures made during its parliamentary enactment echoes the standpoint of *Vythialingam J.* that 'we ought not to do so unless **there is such great ambiguity in the words that looking at Hansard alone would be decisive**' (*Sirisena and others v. Kobbekaduwa, Minister of Agriculture and Lands* [1978], 71, parenthesis and emphasis added).

Though a decision from a foreign jurisdiction (hence only *persuasive* and not *binding* on our courts), *Pepper v. Hart* [1993] finds prior confirmation of its *ratio decidendi*, locally, in the prudent words of *Vythialingam J.* (above), albeit declared *obiter*. Thus, *Sriskandarajah J.'s* direct adoption of *Pepper v. Hart's* reasoning in *Gunasekera and others v. Ravi Karunanayake* [2005] was in due conformity with preexisting local precedent.

As the law presently stands in both the United Kingdom and Sri Lanka, whenever a statutory provision remains uncertain in its objective (despite recourse to whatever intrinsic aids of construction), it is legitimate to have recourse to the parliamentary debate that preceded its passing (as an extrinsic aid) in furtherance of ascertaining its true purpose.

3. AMBIGUITY IN THE WORDING OF SECTION 3(1) OF THE BAIL ACT

In *Thilanga Sumathipala v. Inspector-General of Police and others* [2004], it was opined that:

An analytical and critical appraisal of section 3(1) of the English and Sinhala versions of the Bail Act inclines one to the view that the two versions differ in substance. **The Sinhalese version is wider in scope than the English version, which is more restrictive.** When the two sections differ,

it is *sine qua non* that recourse should be to the Sinhala text. (*Per Abeyratne J.*, 224, emphasis added.)

In *Gunasekera and others v. Ravi Karunanayake* [2005], it was likewise observed as follows:

... It appears that there is a discrepancy between the Sinhala text, and the English text and the Sinhala text should prevail over the English text. (*Per Sriskandarajah J.*, 22.)

However, the Sinhala version of section 3(1) presents an inherent incomprehensibility that is not apparent in its English counterpart.

The Sinhala section 3(1) reads as follows:

1979 අංක 48 දරන ත්රස්තවාදය වළැක්වීමේ (තාවකාලික විධිවිධාන) පනත යටතේ හෝ මහජන ආරක්ෂක පනත යටතේ නියෝග යටතේ හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරුවී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තන් ඇප පිට නිදහස් කිරීම සම්බන්ධයෙන් ජරකාශිත විධිවිධාන සලසා ඇත්තේ යම් ලිඛිත නීතියක් යටතේද එම ලිඛිත නීතිය යටතේ හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරුවී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තෙකුට මේ පනතේ සඳහන් කිසිවක් අදාළ නොවේ.

The averred ‘incomprehensibility’ is brought about by the absence of any apparent breaks within the sentence (by way of punctuation or otherwise). This makes it impossible to ascertain which phrases were intended to be read together.

If, as a tentative starting point, the ‘breaks’ are applied after each ‘හෝ’ (meaning ‘or’), the segments would chronologically read as follows:

1979 අංක 48 දරන ත්රස්තවාදය වළැක්වීමේ (තාවකාලික විධිවිධාන) පනත යටතේ හෝ
 මහජන ආරක්ෂක පනත යටතේ නියෝග යටතේ හෝ
 වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ
 වරදකට වරදකරුවී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ

සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තන් ඇප පිට නිදහස් කිරීම සම්බන්ධයෙන් ජරකාශිත විධිවිධාන සලසා ඇත්තේ යම් ලිඛිත නීතියක් යටතේද එම ලිඛිත නීතිය යටතේ හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරුවී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තෙකුට මේ පනතේ සඳහන් කිසිවක් අදාල නොවේ.
 (Emphasis added.)

Admittedly, the above does not serve to provide much in terms of ‘clarification.’

Since ‘suspect-offenders’ – both in their plural and singular forms – are mentioned, applying ‘breaks’ to distinguish between ‘the many’ and ‘the one’ yields the following:

1979 අංක 48 දරන ත්රස්තවාදය වළැක්වීමේ (තාවකාලික විධිවිධාන) පනත යටතේ හෝ මහජන ආරක්ෂක පනත යටතේ නියෝග යටතේ හෝ(.:)
 (1) වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරුවී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තන් ඇප පිට නිදහස් කිරීම සම්බන්ධයෙන් ජරකාශිත විධිවිධාන සලසා ඇත්තේ යම් ලිඛිත නීතියක් යටතේද එම ලිඛිත නීතිය යටතේ හෝ
 (2) වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරුවී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තෙකුට මේ පනතේ සඳහන් කිසිවක් අදාල නොවේ.
 (Emphasis and parentheses added.)

A direct English translation of this linear reading of Singhala 3(1) would thus be:

Nothing in this Act shall apply to(.:)
 (1) any written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of offenses under the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.48 of 1979 or Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance;
 or
 (2) any person accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.48 of 1979 or Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance.

It is crucial to note that the precise English rendering of the words ‘යම් ලිඛිත නීතියක්’ is ‘any written law,’ and not ‘any *other* written law.’ If it were the latter, the corresponding Sinhala text should have read as ‘යම් වෙනත් ලිඛිත නීතියක්’ – ‘වෙනත්’ meaning ‘*other*.’

Thus, when Srisikandarajah *J.* proclaimed – following the dictum of Abeyratne *J.* in *Thilanga Sumathipala v. The Inspector General of Police and others* [2004], 225, para.490 – that ‘any **‘other written law’** in section 3 of the Bail Act refers to the Prevention of Terrorism Act and the Public Security Ordinance, and **no other written law is contemplated by that section’** (*Gunasekera and others v. Ravi Karunanayake* [2005], 22, emphasis added), he obviously had in mind this ‘linear’ meaning of Sinhala 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997].

However, English section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997] seemingly curtails the extensiveness of scope that this ‘linear’ reading of its Sinhala counterpart conveys by prescribing (somewhat elusively) criteria for adding other written law offenses to those already expressed as exempted from its reach.

Hence, a patent ambiguity concerning the Bail Act’s ambit is ‘brought to light’ by the almost diametrically opposed Sinhala and English renditions of section 3(1), the resolution of which would, conventionally, have been in favor of the former. However, since recourse might properly be had to the ‘extrinsic aid’ of pertinent Hansard (*per Gunasekera and others v. Ravi Karunanayake* [2005] and *Shiyam v. Officer In Charge, Narcotics Bureau and another* [2006]), a means for resolving this ambiguity *cum* obscurity does exist.

Per Lord Browne-Wilkinson *J.* (in *Pepper v. Hart* [1993], 640), recourse to Hansard is permitted where (a) a manifest ‘ambiguity,’ ‘obscurity’ or ‘absurdity’ in a statutory provision (b) necessitates reference to statements made in Parliament by a ‘promoter’ of the parent bill, which themselves are (c) ‘clear.’ However, as antecedently determined by Vythialingam *J.* (in

Sirisena and others v. Kobbekaduwa [1978], 71), the *sine qua non* for such recourse is the existence of ‘**such great ambiguity in the words that looking at Hansard alone would be (d) decisive**’ (emphasis and parenthesis added). Thus, *Vythialingam J.* was able to hypothesize not only those criteria enumerated under ‘(a)’ to ‘(b)’ above (prescribed eighteen years later by Lord Browne-Wilkinson *J.*) but also a fourth, namely, decisiveness (‘(d)’ above), all within the confines of an *obiter dictum*.

That a manifest irreconcilability prevails between the Bail Act’s English section 3(1) and its Sinhala counterpart (when read linearly) has already been expressed. Since the two versions are almost diametrically opposed – the Sinhala ‘extending’ and the English ‘confining’ the reach of the Bail Act – ‘intrinsic aids’ to interpretation provide no assistance. Thus, any attempt to reconcile these two divergent versions necessitates reference being made to the parliamentary debate that preceded the Bail Act’s passing into law. This ‘extrinsic aid’ would serve to reveal not only the founding intent common to both versions, but also the extent to which the one or the other has more fully given expression to such intent. Indeed, *per Vythialingam J.*, so ‘great’ is the ‘ambiguity’ – and perhaps so ‘decisive’ would Hansard be – in righting this anomaly.

However, as already noted, *per* Lord Browne-Wilkinson *J.* in *Pepper v. Hart* [1993] above, the (source) words of Hansard to be so ‘relied upon’ should consist of ‘one or more statements **by a minister** or other promoter of the bill’ (640, emphasis added).

Dr. G. L. Peiris, who at all times material to the enacting of the Bail Act [1997] remained the ‘Minister of Justice and Constitutional Affairs’ of Sri Lanka (a Cabinet ministership entailing ‘collective responsibility’), is reported to have declared, at the second reading of the Bail Bill in Parliament, among other things, as follows:

It has been necessary to exclude certain statutory regimes from the ambit of application of this law. The bill, which I have the honor to present, does not apply to the Prevention of Terrorism Act. **Offenses under the Prevention of Terrorism Act are not caught up within the ambit of this law** because there are special considerations applicable to the **safety of the state**. *Salus Civitatis Suprema Lex* has always been an axiom of the law. The **security of the state** is of the highest possible legal value. In recognition of that **reality**, we have refrained, for the moment, from bringing the Prevention of Terrorism Act within the applicability of this particular law. That is a matter to be considered in the future. I am not foreclosing that for all time. These matters are required to be assessed from time to time with changing circumstances. **But right now we think that the right balance to be struck does not allow us to bring offenses under that particular statutory regime within the four corners of this particular law.** For the same reasons, Mr. Speaker, regulations under **the Public Security Ordinance** will also not be regulated by the provisions contained in this new piece of legislation. **Nor** will this legislation apply to **other** written laws, which contain **express provisions in respect of bail for persons accused of offenses under such laws**. (Hansard 1997, 504-505, emphasis added.)

The Latin maxim *salus civitatis suprema lex* generally translates to *the welfare/health/safety of the people shall be the supreme law*; the ‘Minister’ has confined *salus* to ‘safety’ and synonymously ‘security.’ Thus, the sole reason averred for excluding ‘offenses under the Prevention of Terrorism Act’ (No.48 of 1979) from the ambit of the proposed Bail Act [1997] is their indispensable utility in preserving the ‘security of the state’ by prescribing and penalizing crimes against national security or public order.

Per the ‘Minister,’ what the government had striven to achieve was an optimal ‘balance’ between the *legitimate expectation of pretrial release* and *exceptional restriction thereof* by excluding from the ambit of the proposed Bail Act [1997] only those offenses falling under the specific ‘statutory regime’ of crimes against national security or public order.³

A ‘statutory regime’ is generally understood to mean a comprehensive system of rules and procedures established through written laws enacted by a legislative body for governing a specific subject area, which in this instance is unequivocally the ‘safety of the state.’

Accordingly, offenses under ‘that particular statutory regime’ could only connote crimes against national security or public order, as confirmed by the ‘Minister’s’ further example of those extraordinarily created by regulations promulgated under the Public Security Ordinance (No.25 of 1947).

Most pertinent to the proper interpretation of section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997] is the ‘Minister’s’ averment that, ‘**Nor** will this legislation apply to **other** written laws which contain **express provisions in respect of bail** for persons accused of **offenses under such laws** (emphasis added).’ The conjunction ‘nor,’ which the ‘Minister’ has chosen to commence his sentence with, constitutes a usage in British English meaning ‘neither’: ‘~~Nor~~ *Neither* will this legislation apply to other written laws which contain express provisions in respect of bail for persons accused of **offenses** under such laws’ (obliteration, italicized interpolation and emphasis added). This presupposes that the inapplicability of the proposed Bail Act to a distinct type of offense under written law has already been proclaimed, which is plainly the case *per* the ‘Minister’s’ explicit ousting of ‘that particular statutory regime’ of crimes against the ‘safety of the state’ (exemplified by those prescribed by the Prevention of Terrorism Act and, ‘**for the same reasons,**’ the Public Security Ordinance’s Regulations). This ‘inapplicability’ of the proposed Bail Act is patently extended to like offenses (*i.e.*, offenses of the same genus, namely those against national security or public order) by the ‘Minister’s’ said usage of ‘**nor,**’ **provided that** special ‘provisions in respect of bail’ have been ‘expressed’ for them.

Thus, *per* the ‘Minister,’ an offense under any other written law would be exempt from the proposed Bail Act’s purview only upon (**a**) being fundamentally classifiable as one inherently against national security or public order and (**b**) having a grant of bail expressed in respect thereof under its parent law. Notably, the proposed Bail Act’s inapplicability has been made contingent on the **nature of the offense and not the nature of its parent law**. Accordingly, no matter what the description of the parent law – whether it provides predominantly for

matters concerning national security or public order or not – an offense against the ‘safety of the state,’ when prescribed thereunder, would remain exempt from the purview of the Bail Act [1997], **provided that** bail is obtainable for the same under such law. Thus, when the Bail Bill was passed into law, it was this intent regarding the extent of its reach, as declared by the ‘Minister,’ that received the majority of Parliament’s approval.

As already determined *via* both an individual and comparative analysis, the ‘linearly’ read Sinhala section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997] deviates not only from the meaning of its English counterpart but also from that intended to be conveyed by the source words in Hansard (cited immediately above). English section 3(1), though worded to convey a meaning proximate to that of its ‘source words,’ still falls short of their ideal connotation.

Hence, an effort must be made to elicit a reading of each version that conveys the full meaning of its ‘source words’ in Hansard while doing the least violence, if at all, to its respective language.

4. RESOLVING THE AMBIGUITY BY ANALOGICAL REASONING

Since the ‘Minister’ proceeded to express the legislative intent underlying the provisions of the Bail Act [1997] – including that regarding section 3(1) – in English rather than Sinhala, the English version of section 3(1) takes precedence.

Nothing in this Act shall apply to any person accused or suspected of having committed, or convicted of, **an offense under**, the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act. No 48 of 1979, Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance or any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed, or convicted of, offenses under such other written law. (Emphasis added.)

Since the very concept of bail pertains exclusively to an offense, it comes as no surprise that the operative focus of the provision is on ‘an offense under ... written law.’ This is wholly in accordance with the legislative intent concerning the scope of the proposed Bail Act [1997] as declared by the ‘Minister’ and recorded in Hansard (see above), most pertinently with his averment, ‘the right balance to be struck does not allow us to bring **offenses** under that particular statutory regime within the four corners of this particular law’ (emphasis added). The **type of offense, not its parent law**, is what this provision pivots on. Accordingly, the following superficial expansion of section 3(1)’s wording is warranted:

Nothing in this Act shall apply to any person accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of(:

an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism ... Act. No 48 of 1979,

(an offense under) Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance or

(an offense under) any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of offenses under such other written law. (Emphasis and parentheses added.)

The legislature’s underlying intent to focus on the **offense**, in preference to its parent written law, is thus brought to the fore *via* this most basic expanding of the drafter’s simplified (for brevity) listing; no violence is done to the language hereby.

In the ‘Minister’s’ own words (*per* Hansard 1997, 504-505): **(a)** an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism Act shall not be caught up within the proposed Bail Act’s ambit because of ‘**special considerations applicable to the safety of the state**’; **(b)** ‘**for the same reasons**,’ an offense under the Public Security Ordinance’s Regulations shall not fall within its purview (emphasis added); and **(c)** offenses under these written laws shall remain beyond the proposed Bail Act’s reach owing to their belonging to a ‘**particular statutory regime**’ of offenses: those against national security or public order (emphasis added). It necessarily follows that for ‘an offense under any other written law’ to be exempted from the scope of

the Bail Act [1997], *per* section 3(1) of the same, it must be one that is inherently against national security or public order. Hence, whatever the nature or description of a written law, a crime constituted thereunder in order to gain exclusion from the Bail Act's operation must be one of the same kind as those against national security or public order.

It is toward establishing **an affinity among offenses – not written laws** – that preference has unequivocally been given: 'But right now we think that the right balance to be struck does not allow us to bring **offenses** under that particular statutory regime (which secures the 'safety of the state') within the four corners of this particular law' (*per* the 'Minister' in the *aforecited* Hansard with emphasis and parenthesis added). Hence, **it is the offenses that need to be of the same kind, not their parent laws.**

Thus, *per* the plain intent of the legislature, section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997] should be more fully reread as follows:

Nothing in this Act shall apply to any person accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of(:

(1) an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism ... Act. No 48 of 1979,

(2) (*an offense under*) Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance or

(3) (*an offense of the same kind (i.e., against national security or public order) under*) any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of offenses under such other written law.

(Parentheses added.)

Support for this construction is derived further from those prior wordings used by our own legal draftsmen to convey the legislature's intention to establish affinity not only among existing similar offenses but also between extant and future ones:

A person may be refused a license or permit ... (b) **if he has been convicted of an offense under this Act, or of an offense under any other written law which was committed in connection with**

the possession or use of any gun or explosive or in the commission of which any gun or explosive was used (Explosives Act No.21 of 1956, section 14(3), emphasis added.)

No person shall be qualified to be an elector at an election of the President, or of the Members of Parliament or to vote at any Referendum, if he is subject to any of the following disqualifications, namely – ... (f) if a period of five years has not elapsed since – (i) the last of the dates, if any, of **his being convicted of any offense under the provisions of sections 77 to 82 (both inclusive) of the Local Authorities Elections Ordinance or for such offense under any future law as would correspond to any offense under the said sections;** or (ii) the last of the dates, if any, of his being convicted of an offense under the provisions of sections 2 and 3 of the Public Bodies (Prevention of Corruption) Ordinance or of such offense under any future law as would correspond to the said offense (Constitution of the Republic of Sri Lanka [1978], Article 89 (f), emphasis added.)

No person shall be qualified to be an elector at an election of the President, or of the Members of Parliament or to vote at any Referendum, if he is subject to any of the following disqualifications, namely – ... (i) if a period of seven years has not elapsed since – (i) the date of **his being convicted of any offense under the provisions of sections 188 to 201 (both inclusive) of the Penal Code (Ordinance No.2 of 1883) or for such other offense under any future law as would correspond to any offense under the said sections ...** . (Constitution of the Republic of Sri Lanka [1978], Article 89(i), emphasis and parenthesis added.)

As declared by the ‘Minister’ and promulgated under section 3(1), the written parent law of any corresponding offense must expressly provide for bail in respect thereof. The need for ‘express provisions in respect of the release on bail of persons accused, suspected or convicted’ is prescribed not as a definitive trait of any envisaged category, but as the *sine qua non* for the Bail Act’s general inapplicability to special laws providing for special bail so as to obviate legislative superfluousness or redundancy.⁴ Absent such a provision, the offense loses its immunity from the Bail Act’s application.

With regard to all other crimes not inherently concerned with national security or public order, the provisions of the Bail Act [1997] shall apply residually, as the general law (or ‘codified common law’), limited only by whatever unequivocally expressed special provisions to the

contrary. In effect, the said *sine qua non* acts as a proviso that could be tentatively interpolated into said section 3(1) as follows:

Nothing in this Act shall apply to any person accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of(:

(1) an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism ... Act. No 48 of 1979,

(2) (*an offense under*) Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance or

(3) (*an offense – against national security or public order – under*) any other written law ~~which~~ *provided that such other written law* makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of *like* offenses under such other written law. (Parentheses, obliteration and italicized interpolations added.)

Some violence is indeed done to the legislature's enacted words hereby, albeit solely in furtherance of presenting the legislature's true intent.⁵

From all of the foregoing, it appears that to give effect morefully to the sovereign legislature's intent underlying section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997], an altered reading of the same would have to be preferred, arguably, as follows:

Nothing in this Act shall apply to any person accused, or suspected of having committed, or convicted of, an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.48 of 1979 or an offense under Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance or an offense against national security or public order under any other written law, provided that such other written law makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of like offenses under such other written law. (Simplified.)

Obviously, the Sinhala version of said section 3(1) would now have to be reread in accordance with the above. In its present form, it reads thus:

1979 අංක 48 දරන ත්රස්තවාදය වළැක්වීමේ (තාවකාලික විධිවිධාන) පනත යටතේ හෝ මහජන ආරක්ෂක පනත යටතේ නියෝග යටතේ හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරුවී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තන් ඇප පිට නිදහස් කිරීම සම්බන්ධයෙන් ජරකාශිත විධිවිධාන

සලසා ඇත්තේ යම් ලිඛිත නීතියක් යටතේද එම ලිඛිත නීතිය යටතේ හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරුවී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තෙකුට මේ පනතේ සඳහන් කිසිවක් අදාළ නොවේ.

When the drafter’s simplified (for brevity) listing is expanded, with no violence being done to the language, it reads as follows:

1979 අංක 48 දරන ත්‍රස්තවාදය වළැක්වීමේ (තාවකාලික විධිවිධාන) පනත යටතේ වරදකට හෝ මහජන ආරක්ෂක පනත යටතේ නියෝග යටතේ වරදකට හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරු වී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තන් ඇප පිට නිදහස් කිරීම සම්බන්ධයෙන් ජරකාශිත විධිවිධාන සලසා ඇත්තේ යම් ලිඛිත නීතියක් යටතේ ද එම ලිඛිත නීතිය යටතේ වරදකට හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරු වී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තෙකුට මේ පනතේ සඳහන් කිසිවක් අදාළ නොවේ.

(Expanded with underlined interpolations.)

Indeed, it is a welcome relief to observe that this expanded Sinhala version could be rendered commensurate with its duly altered English version (presented above) simply by adding the suffix ‘ව’ (to the word ‘තැනැත්තන්’) and adjective ‘එවැනිම’ (to the end of ‘එම ලිඛිත නීතිය යටතේ’), as follows:

1979 අංක 48 දරන ත්‍රස්තවාදය වළැක්වීමේ (තාවකාලික විධිවිධාන) පනත යටතේ වරදකට හෝ මහජන ආරක්ෂක පනත යටතේ නියෝග යටතේ වරදකට හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරු වී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තන්ව ඇප පිට නිදහස් කිරීම සම්බන්ධයෙන් ජරකාශිත විධිවිධාන සලසා ඇත්තේ යම් ලිඛිත නීතියක් යටතේ ද එම ලිඛිත නීතිය යටතේ එවැනිම වරදකට හෝ වරදක් සිදුකර ඇති බවට හෝ වරදකට වරදකරු වී ඇති බවට චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තෙකුට, මේ පනතේ සඳහන් කිසිවක් අදාළ නොවේ.

(Expanded with underlined interpolations.)

Simplified, the above reads as:

1979 අංක 48 දරන ත්‍රස්තවාදය වළැක්වීමේ (තාවකාලික විධිවිධාන) පනත යටතේ වරදකට හෝ මහජන ආරක්ෂක පනත යටතේ නියෝග යටතේ වරදකට හෝ වරදක රුවී ඇති, චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තන්ව ඇප පිට නිදහස් කිරීම සම්බන්ධයෙන් ජරකාශිත විධිවිධාන සලසා ඇත්තේ යම්

ලිඛිත නීතියක් යටතේ ද එම ලිඛිත නීතිය යටතේ එවැනිම වරදකට හෝ වරදකරුවී ඇති, චෝදනා ලැබ සිටින හෝ සැක කරනු ලබන තැනැත්තෙකුට, මේ පනතේ සඳහන් කිසිවක් අදාළ නොවේ.
(Emphasis added.)

Thus, Srisikandarajah *J.*'s opinion that 'the said ambiguity (in the) Singhala text of the Bail Act could be resolved by considering the intention of the legislature' (*Gunasekera and others v. Ravi Karunanayake* [2005], 27, parenthesis added) holds true. The 'best evidence' of legislative intent that underlies a specific provision of law is to be found in those words expressed in furtherance thereof as recorded in Hansard.

When recourse is accordingly had to a legal provision's 'source words' to 'resolve' an 'ambiguity' that prevails within their translated and/or redacted words as enacted, the conclusion so reached is one produced by 'analogous' reasoning, not *stricto sensu* 'legal' reasoning. Thus, by merely referring (analogically) to the pertinent legislative intent divulged in Hansard, the provision imperfectly enacted by the wording of section 3(1) was capable of being perfected.

Accordingly, all offenses, other than those *inherently against national security or public order having appertaining bail provisions expressed in their parent laws*, would justly fall within the purview of the Bail Act [1997] from 28th November 1997 onward. Any exhaustion of offenses so *excludable* from the purview of the Bail Act would have no bearing whatsoever on those so *includable*.

5. RESOLVING THE AMBIGUITY BY LEGAL REASONING

Ascertaining the underlying intent of a statutory provision by having recourse to well-established rules and principles of interpretation, without incurring any violence to the legislature's language whatsoever, is what is contemplated hereunder. Nonetheless, the

‘source words’ in Hansard are construed as both providing the backdrop for, and pointing the direction in which, such ‘legal’ reasoning should proceed.

However, since the ‘linear’ reading of the Sinhala version of section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997] conflicts with its ‘source words’ in Hansard – the latter exempting generic offenses that the former does not – only the English version of section 3(1) warrants consideration under this black letter law approach.

As already noted, the enacted English section 3(1) reads thus:

Nothing in this Act shall apply to any person accused or suspected of having committed, or convicted of, an offense under, the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.48 of 1979, Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance or any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed, or convicted of, offenses under such other written law.

It has also been noted that when the above is duly expanded (for ease of construction), without violence to its language, the following manifests:

Nothing in this Act shall apply to any person accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of:
 an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act. No 48 of 1979,
an offense under Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance or
an offense under any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of offenses under such other written law. (Italicized text interpolated.⁶)

These expanded words unequivocally declare the Bail Act’s inapplicability to ‘an’ offense (not ‘any’ offense) under the Prevention of Terrorism Act, as well as to ‘an’ offense (not ‘any’ offense) under Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance.⁷ They further declare

the Bail Act's inapplicability to 'an' offense (not 'any' offense) under any other written law expressing provision in respect of bail for offenses under the same.

The provision's intent to group offenses prescribed by the Prevention of Terrorism Act along with those promulgated *via* the Public Security Ordinance's Regulations is clearly warranted, owing to the similarity in their underlying common objective: *to secure both the state and its public from threatened and actual anarchy*.⁸

However, the provision's intent to additionally accommodate offenses under any other written law within this select group, strongly suggests an indispensability to have such additional offenses share the same objective found common to the former two (*viz., to secure both the state and its public from threatened and actual anarchy*). No necessity would otherwise have arisen to provide *two* specific examples of laws addressing offenses against national security or public order (both severally and in the aggregate).

Furthermore, if the condition imposed on all contemplated offenses of this kind – that *provision for bail be expressed in respect thereof under their respective parent laws* – were instead deemed the 'definitive' attribute of a contemplated class⁹ of crimes, then the mentioning of two from the same subdivision (*offenses against national security or public order*) only, as opposed to one each from at least two/three subdivisions (*e.g., offenses concerning dangerous drugs, offenses concerning offensive weapons, offenses concerning immigration and emigration, etc.*), becomes transgressive thereof.

Thus, the *ejusdem generis* principle, which prescribes this very imperative *to abstain from rendering redundant the criterion by which a lawmaker has decided to associate specific entities to the exclusion of others*, becomes aptly invocable in this regard.

Originating in ancient Rome and evolving through various European legal traditions, this ‘genus species rule of language construction’ came to be espoused by English common law and bequeathed to commonwealth jurisdictions, including Sri Lanka, wherein its influence prevails.

Although the ‘New Law Reports’ do evince many occasions on which Sri Lanka’s courts have had recourse to this principle of interpretation, a detailed explanation regarding its application has been provided by only a few superior court justices: Garvin *J.* in the matter of the trial of *Thomas Perera alias Banda* [1927] 29 N.L.R. 6, 8; Jayewardene *A.J.* in *Vaitalingham v. Holland-Colombo Trading Society* [1932] 34 N.L.R. 169, 174; Wijayatilake *J.* in *Captain v. Commissioner of Inland Revenue* [1974] 77 N.L.R. 350, 351; *etc.* Among them, Ranasinghe *J.*’s succinct yet comprehensive expounding of the same (based on Bindra 1975, 273, 280, 282, 285-6) remains particularly instructive:

The rule of *ejusdem generis* is that, **where particular words are followed by general words, the general words should not be construed in their widest sense but should be held as applying to objects, persons or things of the same general nature or class as those specifically enumerated**, unless of course there is a clear manifestation of a contrary purpose. It is only a ‘rule of construction’ which enables a court to ascertain the intention of the legislature when the intention is not clear. **It should not be resorted to for the purpose of defeating the intention of the legislature but for the purpose of elucidating the words and giving effect to its intention.** It will not apply where the specific words do not come under a class or category, nor where the whole scheme of the enactment and the object and the mischief of the enactment do not require such a **restricted** meaning to be attached to the words of the general import. **There must be a distinct genus or category.** The specific words must apply not to different objects of a widely differing character but to something which must be called a ‘class’ or ‘kind’ of objects. Further, **if the particular words exhaust the whole genus, as for instance, where the specific words embrace all the persons or objects of the class designated by the enumeration, the general words take on a meaning beyond the class.** (*Jinawathie v. Emalin Perera* [1986], 131-132, emphasis added.)

Despite the numerous pages penned by eminent jurists in this regard, especially citing many a dictum from English common law, Ranasinghe *J.*'s above summation alone suffices to detail the requisite criteria by which the *ejusdem generis* principle could be invoked and utilized within section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997].

To restate the aforesaid expanded English section 3(1):

Nothing in this Act shall apply to any person accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of:

an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.48 of 1979,

an offense under Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance or

an offense under any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of offenses under such other written law. (Italicized text interpolated.)

'Particular/specific words' ('an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism ... Act' and 'an offense under Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance') are in fact 'followed' by the 'general words' ('an offense under any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail ...') in the expanded section 3(1) above. This suffices to tentatively raise the *ejusdem generis* principle *per* Ranasinghe *J.*'s aforesaid dictum. *Per* the same dictum, 'general words ... should be held as applying to ... the same general nature or class as those specifically enumerated'; also, 'there must be a distinct genus or category.'

Accordingly, said section 3(1)'s general words, 'an offense under any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail ... ,' are required to be construed as confining themselves to **(a)** an offense that is generically similar to one prescribed by the Prevention of Terrorism Act and/or Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance and **(b)** for which release on bail has been already provided for by way of express provision in its parent law. For an offense to be 'generically similar,' *per* **(a)** above, it should obviously

concern itself with the objective(s) common to the exemplified written laws, to wit: the preservation of national security or public order.¹⁰

Again, *per* Ranasinghe J., *ibidem*, since ‘general words **should not** be construed in their widest sense’ (emphasis added), the possible alternate recourse of deeming *offenses which have express provisions in respect of bail made by their parent laws* the ‘operative genus’ of the said section 3(1) is, *ipso facto*, rendered untenable.

Furthermore, section 2 of the Bail Act [1997] categorically states that ‘the **guiding principle** in the implementation of the **provisions** of this Act shall be that the grant of **bail shall be regarded as the rule and the refusal to grant bail as the exception**’ (emphasis and parenthesis added). As section 3(1) is, indeed, a ‘provision of this Act,’ it is naturally subject to this ‘guiding principle.’ Thus, when interpreting said section 3(1), the preferred construction – no less than *per* enacted legislative intent – would have to be one that operates to widen and not narrow the reach of the Bail Act; in other words, to decrease, not increase, the number of offenses exempted from the applicability of the Bail Act.

If the operative genus of the said section 3(1) were held to be *offenses for which their parent laws make express provision in respect of bail*, entailing exclusion from the Bail Act’s purview of all ‘special law’ offenses notwithstanding their association/disassociation with national security or public order, the ‘guiding principle’ underlying said section 3(1) (and others) that *bail be the rule and refusal the exception* would come to be compromised in its efficacy. *Per* Ranasinghe J., *ibidem*, the *ejusdem generis* principle ‘**should not** be resorted to for the purpose of **defeating** the intention of the legislature’ (emphasis added).

Hence, ‘an offense under any other written law,’ as prescribed by said section 3(1), must **(a)** inherently be one against national security or public order and **(b)** have provision for bail

expressed in respect thereof by its parent Act, in order to be duly ousted from the purview of the Bail Act [1997].

The Bail Act came into force on 28th November 1997. At such time, the only other crimes against national security or public order were those prescribed and penalized under the Penal Code Ordinance No.2 of 1883 (hereinafter 'Penal Code [1883]'), particularly under its 'Chapter VI,' entitled 'Of Offenses Against The State,' and 'Chapter VIII,' entitled 'Of Offenses Against The Public Tranquility.' However, the granting of bail in respect of these generic offenses was not vested in the 'parent' Penal Code [1883], but in the Code of Criminal Procedure Act No.15 of 1979, a complementary but separate written law. This omission on the part of their 'parent law' to encompass any provision on bail within its four corners made these generic offenses under the Penal Code [1883] ineligible for exclusion from the ambit of the Bail Act, notwithstanding their being crimes against national security or public order.

Accordingly, at the time of the Bail Act's coming into force, the 'operative genus' prescribed under said section 3(1) – to wit: crimes against national security or public order – was duly represented not only by offenses under (i) the Prevention of Terrorism Act and (ii) Public Security Ordinance's Regulations, being 'specifically enumerated' (*per* Ranasinghe J., *ibidem*), but also by offenses under (iii) 'Chapter VI' and 'Chapter VIII' of the Penal Code [1883], being 'of the same general nature or class as those specifically enumerated' (*per* Ranasinghe J., *ibidem*).

Furthermore, since 'those specifically enumerated' under said section 3(1), namely, 'an offense under the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.48 of 1979' and 'an offense under Regulations made under the Public Security Ordinance,' did not 'embrace all' the offenses 'of the class designated by the enumeration' (those under the said 'Chapters' of the Penal Code [1883] not receiving even indirect mention), in no manner whatsoever was

occasion had to ‘exhaust the whole genus’ (*per* Ranasinghe J., *ibidem*). *Per* the norms pertaining to the application of *ejusdem generis* alone, no necessity arose for the general words of said section 3(1) (‘an offense under any other written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail ...’) to ‘take on a meaning *beyond* the class’ (*per* Ranasinghe J., *ibidem*).

From the perspective of syntax, the phrase, ‘which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed or convicted of offenses under such other written law’ – being part of the general words of said section 3(1) – constitutes a *nonessential adjective clause* that serves to modify **only** the immediately preceding *noun phrase*, ‘any other written law.’ The *noun phrase* – ‘an offense,’ which precedes ‘any other written law,’ remains unaffected thereby; its *ejusdem generis* attribute, imparted by the legislature, prevails. Hence, the phrases ‘an offense’ and ‘any other written law’ are plainly severable.

Upholding this unprejudiced and uncompromised application of *ejusdem generis* to said section 3(1), so as to include **all offenses** – in furtherance of duly enforcing the specifically legislated ‘guiding principle’ for all ‘provisions’ of the Bail Act [1997] that *bail be the rule and refusal the exception* – other than those *inherently against national security or public order having appertaining bail provisions expressed in their parent laws*, would, admittedly, have been the proper recourse. The prescribed exclusion, though unrealizable at the time of the Bail Act’s coming into force – owing to the absence of any amenable offenses other than those specified¹¹ – should ideally have been deferred to take effect eventually, as and when the legislature thought fit to provide for this ‘absence’ either directly or delegatedly. In view of the temporal qualifier ‘for the time being in force’¹² being decidedly **left out** of the general words of said section 3(1), the intended exclusion was clearly enabled to apply to both existing and future provisions.

In fact, espousing such an ‘updating’ or ‘dynamic’ approach to the interpretation of provisions under written laws has been justified as follows:

... Parliament may, and often does, evince an intention that the meaning to be attributed to its words should not be ossified on the day on which they were enacted (Cross 1976, 46.)

... Legislation that is enacted to regulate an ongoing activity over an indefinite period of time invites a dynamic interpretation (Sullivan 2002, 113.)

Parliament, in the wording of an enactment, is expected to anticipate developments over time and drafters will try to foresee the future, and allow for it in the wording. However, the court may apply an updating construction even if the drafter’s efforts in this regard have not been successful. (Baily and Norbury 2017, 409.)

Incidentally, *if* the aforesaid ‘temporal qualifier’ had been incorporated, the general words of said section 3(1) would have read (in all probability) as ‘an offense under any other written law *for the time being in force* which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail ...’ (phrase in italics interpolated). In this eventuality, other generic offenses under parent laws that prescribed bail in respect thereof would have had to be prosecutable upon the Bail Act’s coming into force, *per* the ‘temporal qualifier.’ There being no offenses complying with the entirety of the said description in existence, let alone ‘prosecutable,’ by such time, section 3(1)’s intended exclusion of other amenable offenses would have been rendered a nullity: a dead letter law. The prescribed legislative intent having become ‘frustrated’ by ‘impossibility’ (owing to the unenforceability of the prescribed *sine qua non* that the parent laws of existing generic offenses need mandatorily provide for bail in respect thereof, but not the uninvocability of *eiusdem generis*), it would *then* have been incumbent to pursue an alternative, broader, construction so as not to ‘leave without effect any part of the language’ of said section 3(1).¹³

However, no such ‘temporal qualifier’ was ever employed within said section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997]; a pressing need to depart from the intended *ejusdem generis* reading never arose. Moreover, no prejudice whatsoever would have been caused thereby (*i.e.*, by this *ejusdem generis* reading of section 3(1)) to any extant (or future) special laws that enforced (or sought to enforce) substantive and/or procedural curtailments on grants of bail more restrictive than those prescribed by the Bail Act [1997], as due deference to the *generalia specialibus non derogant*¹⁴ (*generality does not affect specificity*) would have served to preserve their efficacy, subject only to the inviolable ceiling on remand custody prescribed by section 16 read with section 17 of the Bail Act [1997] (see below).

Nonetheless, since its intended (genus and *sine qua non* based) exclusion remained unrealizable for want of even a single amenable offense (other than those specified) to which it could lawfully apply at the time of the Bail Act’s coming into force, the maxim ‘the law does nothing in vain’ (*lex nihil frustra facit*)¹⁵ was thought apt to be invoked to desist from ‘qualifying’ (by way of *ejusdem generis*, *noscitur a sociis* or otherwise) the language of said section 3(1) and instead construe it ‘ordinarily’ and ‘naturally.’¹⁶

Accordingly, from 29th March 2006 onward (*per Shiyam v. Officer-In-Charge, Narcotics Bureau and another* [2006]), said section 3(1) has been understood as excluding from the Bail Act’s purview ‘any person accused or suspected of having committed, or convicted of an offense under ... any ... written law which makes express provision in respect of the release on bail of persons accused or suspected of having committed, or convicted of, offenses under such other written law.’ The Bail Act’s applicability has since been confined, in the main, to Penal Code [1883] offenses.

6. 'UPDATING' SECTION 3(1) OF THE BAIL ACT

As has already been noted, when the Bail Act [1997] came into operation, there was no other offense against national security or public order whose parent law expressly provided for bail in respect thereof. Consequently, the exclusion prescribed by section 3(1) could not be enforced as ideally intended. Accordingly, the proverbial *door* to extending the Bail Act's reach to all offenses except those so excludable came to be *closed*.

It has also been noted that this 'ideally intended' exclusion, though unrealizable when the Bail Act came into force, should have been deferred to take effect eventually, as and when the legislature thought fit to provide for the said absence of other offenses, either directly or delegatedly. Hence, whether the legislature did 'eventually' legislate for this 'absence' remains to be ascertained.

Section 3(1) of Sri Lanka's International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) Act No.56 of 2007 (hereinafter 'ICCPR Act [2007]'), which came into force on 16th November 2007, provides that:

No person shall (**a**) propagate war or (**b**) advocate national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence. (Parentheses and emphasis added.)

Since the preamble to this ICCPR Act [2007] declares *inter alia* that 'it has become necessary ... to enact appropriate legislation to give effect to those civil and political rights referred to in the aforesaid Covenant, for which no adequate legislative recognition has yet been granted,' the said section 3(1) constitutes a joinder of Articles 20(1)¹⁷ and 20(2)¹⁸ of the parent *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* [1966] for purposes of incorporating the same into the law of Sri Lanka.

A prohibition on disseminating communications that precipitate the breakdown of public order is the gist of what the designated limb '**(b)**' of the aforesaid section 3(1) of the ICCPR Act [2007] conveys. The following extant offenses under Sri Lankan law also convey the same gist:

(a) Any person who ... by words either spoken or intended to be read or by signs or by visible representations or otherwise causes or intends to cause commission of acts of violence or religious, racial or communal disharmony or feelings of ill-will or hostility between different communities or racial or religious groups ... shall be guilty of an offense under this Act. (Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.48 of 1979, section 2(1)(h).)

(b) No person shall, by word of mouth or by any written, electronic, digital or other means whatsoever, including through any media, information and communication technology, automated system or artificial intelligence system, communicate, publish, generate or disseminate any rumor or false statement which is likely to cause public alarm or public disorder. (The 'Emergency (Miscellaneous Provisions and Powers) Regulations' promulgated *via* the Gazette (Extraordinary) of the Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka, No.2464/31, dated Friday, 28th November 2025, Regulation 20.)

(c) Whoever by words, either spoken or intended to be read, or by signs, or by visible representations, or otherwise ... attempts to raise discontent or disaffection amongst the People of Sri Lanka, or to promote feelings of ill-will and hostility between different classes of such People, shall be punished with simple imprisonment for a term which may extend to two years. (Penal Code Ordinance No.2 of 1883, section 120.)

Evidently, the offense constituted under limb '**(b)**' of section 3(1) of the ICCPR Act [2007] is of the same kind as those enumerated under '**(a)**,' '**(b)**' and '**(c)**' above: 'offenses against public order,' which is one constituent subgenus of 'offenses against national security or public order.' Correspondingly, the offense constituted under limb '**(a)**' of section 3(1) of the ICCPR Act [2007] – 'no person shall propagate war' – being a crime against national security, belongs to the other constituent subgenus of 'offenses against national security.' Thus, when limbs '**(a)**' and '**(b)**' combine, the genus 'offenses against national security or public order' becomes fully represented. Also, section 3(4) of the same ICCPR Act [2007] states that this disjunctive

offence 'shall be cognizable and **non-bailable**, and no person suspected or accused ... shall be enlarged on bail, **except by the High Court in exceptional circumstances**' (emphasis added).

It will be recalled that, to duly invoke the exemption from the Bail Act's ambit granted by section 3(1), the offense under any other written law should (**a**) inherently be one against national security or public order and (**b**) have provision for bail expressed in respect thereof by its parent Act. The preceding paragraph has made it abundantly clear that both the requirement that the subject offense be of the same genus ('**a**' above) and the requirement that the parent Act sanction bail in respect thereof ('**b**' above) have been duly fulfilled by the crime created under section 3(1) of the ICCPR Act [2007].

Thus, by 16th November 2007 – less than two years after the general words of said section 3(1) were authoritatively afforded an 'ordinary' and 'natural' reading as opposed to a 'narrower' one – the legislature did fill the void that had impaired the same words from taking effect qualifiedly, as originally intended. It did so by creating, under section 3(1) of the ICCPR Act [2007], an offense against national security or public order that was also eligible for exceptional bail under its parent Act, thereby ensuring full compliance with the dual criteria in section 3(1) of the Bail Act [1997] for excluding such crimes from its purview. This, in turn, enabled and enforced the much belated qualifying of 'an offense under any other written law' appearing in said section 3(1) as originally intended by the legislature. Consequently, only those crimes against national security or public order having appertaining bail provisions specially declared under their respective parent laws find themselves *excluded* from the Bail Act's ambit – all others are *included*.

The Online Safety Act No.9 of 2024 (certified on 1st February 2024) has followed suit. Under section 12, the Act prescribes an offense against national security or public order; under

section 43(b) read with section 39, it declares this offense ‘bailable’ by either the Magistrate’s Court or the High Court.

Accordingly, from 16th November 2007 onward, the hitherto *closed* proverbial *door* – extending the Bail Act’s reach to all extant and future offenses under Sri Lanka’s written laws (saving those expressly excluded and excludable *per* section 3(1)’s ‘(a)’ and ‘(b)’ criteria, above) – came to be *opened*.

As has hitherto been noted, this proverbial *opening* of the *door* would not in any manner prejudice the efficacy of any special law that enforces substantive and/or procedural curtailments on bail more restrictive than those prescribed by the Bail Act [1997] as the principle *generalia specialibus non derogant* (*generality does not affect specificity*) would operate to preserve them, subject only to the inviolable ceiling on remand custody prescribed by section 16 read with section 17 of the Bail Act, evidently legislated in furtherance of Article 9(3) of the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* [1966] (see below).

While the ‘long title’ to Sri Lanka’s ICCPR Act [2007] declares itself ‘an Act to give effect to certain Articles in the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* (ICCPR) relating to human rights which have not been given recognition through legislative measures,’ its ‘preamble’ elaborates thereon by stating: ‘... **Whereas a substantial part of the civil and political rights referred to in that Covenant have been given legislative recognition in the Constitution of Sri Lanka, as well as in other legislation enacted by Parliament ... it has become necessary ... to enact appropriate legislation to give effect to those civil and political rights referred to in the aforesaid Covenant, for which no adequate legislative recognition has yet been granted**’ (emphasis added). Thus, it is clear that the ICCPR Act [2007] was intended to provide exclusively for ‘those civil and political rights’ of the *International*

Covenant on Civil and Political Rights [1966] ‘for which no adequate legislative recognition’ had ‘been granted’ by the successive governments of Sri Lanka.

The *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* [1966], which came into force with Sri Lanka on 11th June 1980, provides under Article 9(3), among other things, that ‘Anyone arrested or detained on a criminal charge ... shall be entitled to trial within a reasonable time or to **release**’ (emphasis added).

This general entitlement to ‘trial within a reasonable time or to **release**’ receives no definitive expression whatsoever within any of the provisions of Sri Lanka’s said ICCPR Act [2007]. This Act’s intended purpose being to provide for those rights under the *Covenant* [1966] not already legislated for, the absence therein of any provision declaring an entitlement to ‘trial within a reasonable time or to **release**’ presupposes that this particular ‘entitlement’ had already been legislated for in Sri Lanka (*i.e.*, prior to 16th November 2007).

In fact, the provisions legislated to fully enforce this *Covenant* [1966] entitlement to ‘trial within a reasonable time or to **release**’ are those found under sections 16 and 17 of the Bail Act [1997]. Together, these sections provide that no person shall be held in pretrial (remand) custody for a period in excess of twelve months from the date of his or her arrest, unless, for good and sufficient reasons as recorded, the High Court, on an application by the Attorney-General, extends that custody by a *further* three months, and likewise by *further* three-month increments thereafter until the *maximum further* pretrial custody period of twelve months is reached. Thus, the maximum period for which any individual could be held in pretrial (remand) custody is generally twelve months – or, exceptionally, twenty-four months – from the date of his/her arrest. Analogously, the same sections 16 and 17 of the Bail Act [1997], when read together, impliedly ‘entitle’ every individual to be tried, generally within 12 months and, exceptionally, within 24 months from the date of his or her arrest.

It becomes obvious that the salient entitlement to ‘trial within a reasonable time or to **release**’ – enshrined in Article 9(3) of the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* [1966] – was what Sri Lanka’s legislature chose to incorporate into domestic law in terms of section 16 read with section 17 of the Bail Act [1997]. Being a duly incorporated covenanted ‘entitlement,’ it is domestically binding and inviolable *per* international obligations,¹⁹ save in circumstances specially prescribed by the source international instrument (*e.g.*, a ‘public emergency’). Consequently, the *generalia specialibus non derogant* (*generality does not affect specificity*) principle of interpretation will **not** enable any special law to be understood as overriding this general ‘entitlement’ save in the said ‘specially prescribed’ context.

The only reason for Sri Lanka’s legislature to abstain from making any reference whatsoever to this ‘entitlement’ within the four corners of the ICCPR Act [2007] was the fact that it had already been legislated for under sections 16 and 17 of the Bail Act [1997], confirming the presumption that ‘Parliament is deemed to have legislated **with knowledge of the existing law**’ (Ed. Fitzgerald 1966, 133, emphasis added).

It is indeed quite fortuitous that an Act concerned with incorporating the hitherto unincorporated civil and political rights prescribed by the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* [1966] was responsible for *opening* the Bail Act’s *door* to the vast majority of crimes prescribed by general and special laws in Sri Lanka alike.

Thus, from 16th November 2007 onward, the guiding principle that *bail be the rule and refusal the exception* (*per* Bail Act [1997], section 2) has come to be fully realized.

7. CONCLUSION

A patent ambiguity regarding the Bail Act's ambit was brought to light by the almost diametrically opposed Singhala and English renditions of section 3(1), the resolution of which required recourse to either: **(a)** 'analogous' reasoning (by treating the 'source words' in Hansard both relevant and binding) or **(b)** 'legal' reasoning (by treating the 'source words' in Hansard relevant but non-binding).

Although the conclusion reached by applying either form of reasoning was substantively the same – to wit: the Bail Act [1997] is generally applicable to all written law offenses in Sri Lanka save for those specifically exempted *per* the twofold criteria prescribed by its section 3(1) – the benefits of this 'conclusion' were made realizable, under legal reasoning, only from 16th November 2007 onward, as opposed to 28th November 1997 onward under 'analogous' reasoning.

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NOTES

¹Section 27 of the Bail Act [1997] provides as follows: ‘**The provisions of this Act** shall have effect **notwithstanding anything to the contrary** in the Criminal Procedure Code Act No.15 of 1979 and in any other written law, other than the Release of Remand Prisoners Act No.8 of 1991, and accordingly, in the event of any conflict or inconsistency between the provisions of this Act and such other written law, other than the Release of Remand Prisoners Act No.8 of 1991, the provisions of this Act shall prevail’ (emphasis added). The words ‘the provisions of this Act’ would appear to be a general reference to the entirety of contents enumerated under sections 1 to 28 of the Bail Act. The words ‘notwithstanding anything to the contrary,’ as they appear in said section 27, constitute a *non obstante* clause. Accordingly, it may be said that section 27 of the Bail Act strives to disclose the authority enjoyed by the Bail Act’s provisions *vis-à-vis* that enjoyed by those of other written laws of like description. The Code of Criminal Procedure Act [1979] – *to the extent that it makes general provision for the release of those arrested or remanded*; the Release of Remand Prisoners Act [1991] – *to the extent that it makes general provision for the release of those remanded*; and the Bail Act [1997] – *to the extent that it makes general provision for the release of those anticipating arrest or arrested or remanded*, may all be encompassed under the same genus: general statutes prescribing generally applicable provisions that may be availed of by any individual to vindicate her/his residual right to liberty. Since a *non obstante* clause, too, is generally construed as incapable of widening the scope of the provision to which it attaches, it is indeed implicit that the words ‘other written law,’ as they appear in said section 27, should be read *noscitur a sociis*. Thus, what section 27 in fact intends to lay out, in authoritative terms, is the hierarchy of statutes that provide generally for the release of detained individuals. The superiority enjoyed by the Release of Remand Prisoners Act [1991] over the Bail Act [1997] within this hierarchy is nonetheless clearly acknowledged therein.

²This particular conclusion, drawn by Ranasinghe J., has been sometimes misrepresented as amounting to a declaration that a statement in Hansard cannot be used for any purpose *other than interpreting a statute*.

³*Per* section 15A of the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.48 of 1979, as amended, the main consideration for ordering ‘detention’ in executive (as opposed to judicial) custody ‘until the conclusion of trial’ is whether the same would be ‘in the interests of **national security** or **public order**’ (emphasis added). In fact, the ‘interests of national security or public order’ are what Act No.48 of 1979 was intended to serve. Likewise, the ‘long title’ to the Public Security Ordinance No.25 of 1947 describes it as making provision *inter alia* ‘in the interests of the **public security** and the preservation of **public order**’ (emphasis added). In furtherance thereof, section 5(1) of the Ordinance states *inter alia* that ‘the President may make such regulations ... as appear to him to be necessary or expedient in the interests of **public security** and the preservation of **public order**’ (emphasis added).

⁴The *sine qua non* for ousting the Bail Act's applicability to an individual suspected of committing an offense against national security or public order under any other written law is that such law already provides for his/her eventual release on bail in respect thereof.

⁵It is presumed that the legislature intends the court to apply a construction which rectifies any error in the drafting of the enactment, where required, in order to give effect to the legislative intention' (Baily and Norbury 2017, 425).

⁶Rupert Cross in his book on Statutory Interpretation (1976, 84-98) states thus: 'The judge may read in words which he considers to be necessarily implied by words which are already in the statute ...' (cited with acquiescence in *Gunasekera and others v. Ravi Karunanayake* [2005], 23).

⁷'An' offense is singular and specific, whilst 'any' offense is plural and general.

⁸In considering the preamble and the other provisions of this Act (No.48 of 1979, as amended), it becomes clear that the intention of the legislature in enacting this statute was to establish and **maintain the rule of law and dispel the threat of anarchy**' (*Rahulan v. Attorney General* [2006], 261, *per* Basnayake J., parenthesis and emphasis added).

⁹In taxonomy, 'class' denotes a much broader grouping than 'genus.' The ascending hierarchical ranking from 'more specific' to 'less specific' is: 'species,' 'genus,' 'family,' 'order,' 'class,' and so on. For example, man is a 'species' and mammals are a 'class.'

¹⁰No imperative exists for this attribute to extend to the written law under which it is prescribed. What the legislature intended was *ejusdem generis* 'offenses,' not parent 'laws.'

¹¹A perusal of the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act No.15 of 1979, as amended, reveals that sections 15B and 19 of the same do expressly provide for the release on bail of individuals arrested, indicted or convicted in respect of offenses committed thereunder. Regulations 40(2) and 40(3) of the 'Emergency (Miscellaneous Provisions and Powers) Regulations, No.1 of 2025' (promulgated by the President under Section 5 of the Public Security Ordinance No.25 of 1947) do comparably provide for grants of bail in respect of persons charged for offenses committed thereunder. Similarly, Regulation 34(2) of the 'Emergency (Miscellaneous Provisions and Powers) Regulations, No.1 of 2022,' and Regulations 21(1), 66(2) and 66(3) of the 'Emergency (Miscellaneous Provisions and Powers) Regulations, No.1 of 2019,' make comparable provision.

¹²A ‘draftsman’s favorite,’ featuring in over 200 provisions within the legislative enactments of Sri Lanka.

¹³‘A construction which would leave without effect any part of the language of a statute will normally be rejected’ (Ed. Langan 1972, 36).

¹⁴The principle *generalia specialibus non derogant* sums up the presumption against implied repeal. A subsequent general act does not affect a prior special act by implication. A general provision should yield to a special provision. **When a general act is subsequently passed, it is logical to presume that the legislature has not repealed or modified the former special act unless it appears that the special act again received consideration from Parliament.**’ (*Ghouse v. Ghouse* [1988], 34-35, per Sharvananda C.J., emphasis added.) ‘... It should be kept in mind that when the legislature has given its attention to a separate subject and made provision for it, the presumption is that **a subsequent general enactment is not intended to interfere with the special provision unless it manifests that intention very clearly.** This is expressed by the Latin maxim *generalia specialibus non derogant ...*.’ (*Abeyratne and another v. Manchanayake* [1992], 364, per Wijeyaratne J., emphasis added.)

¹⁵‘Effect must be given, if possible, to all the words used in the statutory provision, for the legislature is deemed not to waste its words or to say anything in vain’ (*Tennekoon v. Somawathie Perera* [1986], 101, per Sharvananda C.J. citing *Quebec Railway, Light, Heat and Power Company Limited v. Vandry and others* [1920], 186, per Lord Sumner J.).

¹⁶‘If there is nothing to modify, alter or **qualify** the language which the statute contains, it must be construed in the **ordinary** and **natural** meaning of the words and sentences’ (*Sirimavo Bandaranaike v. Ranasinghe Premadasa and another* [1992], 130, per Goonewardene J., emphasis added).

¹⁷‘Any propaganda for war shall be prohibited by law (*International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* [1966], Article 20(1)).’

¹⁸‘Any advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence shall be prohibited by law (*International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* [1966], Article 20(2)).’

¹⁹‘Could the state impose ‘a punishment on the petitioner indirectly by keeping him in remand custody for an **uncertain period**? Obviously ... not What would be the position if after the end of the trial the petitioner is found not guilty?’ (*Thilanga Sumathipala v. Inspector-General of Police and others* [2004], 215, per Sripavan J., emphasis added). ‘We accordingly hold that the fundamental rights of the petitioners ... have been infringed ... since the petitioners have been detained in custody merely upon their being produced in court

and incarcerated without a remedy until the conclusion of their trials' (*Sumanadasa and 205 others v. Attorney-General* [2006], 214, per S.N. Silva C.J.).